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Effects Of Inquiry, Problem-Solving And Lecture Methods On Achievement Of Biology Students In Delta Central Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS), Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), and Lecture Method (LM) on the academic achievement of Biology students in Delta Central Senatorial District. Guided by five research questions and corresponding hypotheses, the study employed a quasi-experimental research design. The population consisted of 13,845 senior secondary school students, from which a sample of 251 Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students was selected. The students were randomly assigned to three experimental groups: Inquiry Learning Strategy, Problem-Solving Strategy and Lecture Method Groups. Data collection involved the use of Biology Achievement Test (BAT). The instrument was developed by the researcher and tested for validity and reliability, yielding coefficients of 0.79 for the BAT. The treatment procedures consisted of exposing the experimental groups to their respective instructional strategies for six weeks. Pretest, posttest, and delayed posttest data were collected and analysed using descriptive statistics, of mean and standard deviation, independent sample t-test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test the stated hypotheses, and post-hoc tests to assess differences in achievement. The findings shows (i) a significant difference in the academic achievement scores of students taught using the different instructional strategies with inquiry learning strategy (ILS) showing the highest improvement in students' academic achievement (ii) There was no significant difference in the academic achievement scores between male and female student taught using the strategies (iii) a non-significant interaction effect between instructional strategies and sex was observed for academic achievement. In conclusion, the study confirmed that active learning strategies, such as ILS and PSS, were more effective than traditional lecture-based methods in improving both academic achievements. It is recommended that teachers incorporate these strategies into their instructional practices.

Keywords: Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS), Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), and Lecture Method (LM), academic achievement and sex

INTRODUCTION

Biology is a fundamental science subject that forms the backbone of numerous scientific and health-related careers. It plays a pivotal role in understanding living systems and developing problem-solving skills necessary for national development. Despite its centrality in the school science curriculum,

students' performance in Biology in Nigeria, especially in secondary schools, continues to fall below expectations. Evidence from the WAEC Chief Examiner's reports between 2017 and 2022 indicates a fluctuating but generally moderate performance, with pass rates (A1–C6) of 55.57% in 2017, 55.10% in 2018, 55.63% in 2019, 53.02% in 2020, 50.88% in 2021, and 57.43% in 2022 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023).

This fluctuation in students' performance may be associated with the continuous use of teacher-centered methods such as the lecture method, which has been widely criticized for limiting student engagement, inquiry, and long-term understanding (Ede & Ugwuanyi, 2021). The lecture method primarily encourages rote memorization rather than meaningful learning, often resulting in shallow comprehension, disinterest, and rapid forgetting of taught concepts (Onah & Agbo, 2020). In a subject as practical and exploratory as Biology, such passive method undermine the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills among learners.

Research has increasingly shown that the traditional approach to teaching Biology is insufficient to meet the 21st-century learning demands, especially in an era characterized by information explosion, technological advancements, and the need for scientific innovation (Amadi & Chukwu, 2021). Many students complete secondary school without the ability to apply biological knowledge to real-life problems, suggesting a significant gap between theoretical instruction and practical application (Anyanwu & Ofoha, 2023). This situation is particularly troubling, given the global emphasis on science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education as a catalyst for development.

To address the persistent challenges associated with the fluctuating standard academic achievement in Biology, scholars and educators have increasingly advocated for the adoption of more effective, learner-centred instructional strategies. One such approach is the inquiry learning strategy, which shifts the focus from teacher-led instruction to student-driven exploration. Inquiry learning emphasizes the active involvement of students in the learning process through observation, questioning, and experimentation. Rather than passively receiving information, students are encouraged to investigate scientific concepts, formulate hypotheses, design and conduct experiments, and analyze data to draw conclusions. This approach mirrors the practices of real scientists and cultivates a spirit of curiosity and discovery in learners (Abubakar & Ogunleye, 2021).

Furthermore, the inquiry learning strategy is rooted in constructivist theory, which posits that knowledge is actively constructed by the learner rather than passively absorbed. As students engage in hands-on activities and open-ended investigations, they not only develop a deeper conceptual understanding of Biology but also enhance their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. According to Onukwufor and Eze (2022), inquiry-based instruction fosters meaningful learning of scientific concepts, which are often poorly grasped under traditional teaching methods. Ezeudu, Eze, and Ezeudu (2023) also highlighted that inquiry-based strategies improve student motivation and engagement, leading to better academic outcomes. This approach enables learners to connect theoretical knowledge with practical applications, thereby making learning more relevant and engaging.

Problem-solving strategy promotes higher-order thinking skills by challenging students to synthesize information from multiple sources and apply it in novel contexts. This not only reinforces their existing knowledge but also helps them to internalize new concepts more effectively. Nwachukwu and Alaribe (2023) affirm that the use of problem-solving instruction in Biology has been shown to improve students' analytical abilities and foster a more meaningful grasp of complex biological content. Moreover, this strategy aligns well with curriculum objectives aimed at producing scientifically literate individuals capable of applying their knowledge to solve real-life problems. In the context of fluctuating performance in Biology, integrating problem-solving strategies into classroom instruction could serve as a crucial step toward reversing the trend and promoting lasting academic achievement irrespective of sex.

Sex disparities in science education further complicate efforts to improve students' academic achievement, particularly in Biology. Research has revealed inconsistent findings regarding how male and female students respond to different instructional strategies in science classrooms. Some studies report that male students tend to perform better in science-related subjects, while others find no significant difference, and yet some suggest that female students outperform their male counterparts (Ogbebor &

Nwafor, 2020; Ibe & Ozoemena, 2021). These contradictions make it difficult to generalize the impact of teaching strategies across sexes.

If the current trend of fluctuating achievement with variations due to sex in Biology continues without the introduction of effective and inclusive instructional strategies, the consequences could be far-reaching. Students may remain ill-prepared for higher education and employment in science-related fields, the nation's scientific manpower base will weaken, and the broader objectives of STEM education will remain unmet. It is in view of these challenges that this study seeks to investigate the effects of inquiry and problem-solving learning strategies on the academic achievement of Biology students in Delta Central Senatorial District, with attention to sex dynamics.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the pivotal role of Biology in national development and its relevance to science and health-related careers, students' academic achievement in the subject in Nigeria remain unsatisfactory. Analysis of WAEC results from 2017 to 2022 reveals a persistently moderate pass rate, indicating that a significant number of students fail to meet the required proficiency levels. This underachievement is further exacerbated by poor understanding of biological knowledge beyond examination periods, a situation that undermines long-term academic success and preparedness for higher education or scientific careers.

At the core of this problem lies the continued dominance of the lecture method in Biology instruction. This teacher-centered approach promotes rote memorization at the expense of critical thinking, inquiry, and practical application of knowledge. Consequently, learners often exhibit superficial understanding, low motivation, and limited problem-solving capacity. These deficiencies are particularly alarming in a 21st-century learning context that demands creativity, innovation, and the ability to apply knowledge to real-world challenges. Moreover, the lack of engagement in traditional classrooms fails to foster the deeper cognitive and affective skills necessary for scientific literacy.

Although research has highlighted the promise of learner-centred strategies such as inquiry-based and problem-solving approaches, their adoption in Nigerian secondary schools remains limited. These methods encourage active participation, experimentation, and exploration, enabling students to construct knowledge, think critically, and retain information more effectively. However, evidence on their comparative effectiveness, especially in relation to conventional teaching methods, remains inconclusive—particularly concerning how they influence both male and female students. The problem of this study, therefore, is: Will the application of inquiry and problem-solving learning strategies significantly enhance the academic achievement of Biology students?

Research Questions

The study was directed by the following research questions:

- 1** :What is the difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students taught using inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District?
- 2**: What is the difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the inquiry learning strategy in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District.
- 3**: What is the difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the problem-solving strategy in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District
- 4**: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using lecture method in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District?
- 5**: What is the interaction effect of instructional strategies (inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method) and sex on students' mean academic achievement scores in Biology in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant differences exist in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students exposed to inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and the lecture method in Senior Secondary Schools within Delta Central Senatorial District

H₀₂: There is no significant difference exists in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the inquiry learning strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District

H₀₃: There is no significant difference exists in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the problem-solving strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District

H₀₄: There is no significant interaction effect exists between instructional strategies (inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method) and sex on students' academic achievement in Biology in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District

H₀₅: What is the interaction effect of instructional strategies (inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method) and sex on students' mean academic achievement scores in Biology in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the influence of inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and the lecture method on the academic achievement of Biology students in Senior Secondary Schools within Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design that was adopted for this study was a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest planned variation design. This design was considered appropriate because it allowed the comparison of the effects of different instructional strategies (inquiry, problem-solving, and lecture methods) on students' academic achievement without random assignment of participants to groups. Intact classes were used for the study to maintain the natural classroom setting and avoid disruption to the school schedule, which aligned with ethical considerations in educational research (Salihu & Adeoye, 2021).

The population for the study consisted of all Senior Secondary II (SS II) Biology students in public co-educational secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. Based on the data provided by the Delta State Ministry of Education, the total population of SS II Biology students in the 2024/2025 Session is estimated at 13,845 students spread across eight Local Government Areas in the district (PPEB, 2024).

The sample for this study consists of 251 Senior Secondary School Two SS11 students from the selected six public co-educational secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District. These schools were selected based on certain criteria, including availability of qualified Biology teachers, adequate Biology laboratory facilities, and willingness to participate in the study.

A multistage sampling procedure was used. At the first stage, three Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from the eight LGAs that make up Delta Central Senatorial District. At the second stage, two co-educational public secondary schools were purposively selected from each of the three LGAs. The distribution of sampled schools, their locations, and the number of male and female students in each school.

The instrument was used for data collection in this study: was the Biology Achievement Test (BAT). The instrument was developed by the researcher and consisted of 50 multiple-choice questions each, designed to assess students' understanding of key Biology concepts covered during the intervention. Each item contains a question stem followed by four options labelled A to D, with only one correct answer. The questions are from past West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) question papers with questions from content areas, namely Photosynthesis, Transport System in Plants and Animals, and Nervous Coordination were used. These topics were chosen based on their inclusion in the national Biology curriculum, their importance to the understanding of advanced biological concepts, and their consistent identification in West African Examinations Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners' reports as areas where students typically demonstrate low performance. Items in the BAT were carefully selected to cover various cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy, such as knowledge, comprehension, application, and

analysis. These items were adapted primarily from past West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) question papers on Biology between the years 2010 and 2023.

To establish the relevance, adequacy, and suitability of the instruments that was used for data collection, the researcher conducted face, content, and construct validity analyses.

The reliability of the instrument was established to determine the consistency and stability of the test items in measuring students' achievement in Biology. Two standard procedures were used: the *Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 (KR-21)* for internal consistency and a *test-retest* method for temporal stability. To estimate the internal consistency of the BAT, the instrument was administered to a group of 30 SSII students Ojeta Secondary School, Abraka which was not included in the actual study sample. The *Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 (KR-21)* was employed because the test items were dichotomously scored (i.e., correct/incorrect). The KR-21 formula measures the extent to which all test items assess the same underlying construct—in this case, achievement in Biology. The computed KR-21 reliability coefficient for the BAT was 0.79, which indicates a high level of internal consistency. According to Fraenkel, Wallen, and Hyun (2019), reliability coefficients above 0.70 are considered acceptable for research purposes. Therefore, the BAT was deemed sufficiently reliable for use in the study.

Treatment Procedure

The treatment procedure for this study was carried out systematically to ensure uniformity across groups and the integrity of results. The study involved three groups of students exposed to different instructional strategies: inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving learning strategy, and the lecture method. Six public co-educational secondary schools were purposively selected and randomly assigned to one of the three groups, with two schools per treatment group. The use of intact SSII classes in each school is intended to preserve natural classroom dynamics and prevent disruption of school routines.

Prior to the implementation of the treatment, Biology teachers in the selected schools were recruited as research assistants. These teachers were trained for two days on how to effectively deliver instruction using the specific learning strategies assigned to their schools. To ensure that the teachers for the three groups are matched in terms of ability and other relevant variables, the same teacher training program was conducted for all the teachers, ensuring each group had the same opportunity to understand the instructional strategy they are to implement. The training included the following:

Phase 1: Training of the Teachers using the Teacher's Training Manual

Session 1: Introduction to the Study and Instructional Strategies

- **Objective:** Familiarize research assistants with the study's purpose, methodology, and expected outcomes. Provide an overview of the instructional strategies.
- **Content:**
 - Explanation of the research questions, hypotheses, and objectives.
 - Discussion of the importance of inquiry and problem-solving strategies in Biology instruction.
 - Overview of the three teaching strategies: inquiry, problem-solving, and lecture method.
 - Introduction to the roles and responsibilities of the research assistants.
- **Method:** A lecture was given, followed by group discussions to clarify any questions. A handout summarizing the study design and objectives will be provided.

Session 2: Training on Inquiry Learning Strategy (5E Model)

- **Objective:** Equip research assistants with the skills to implement the inquiry learning strategy using the 5E model (Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate).
- **Content:**
 - Overview of the 5E model and its application to Biology instruction.
 - Step-by-step breakdown of how to engage students, facilitate exploration, explain concepts, and encourage elaboration.
 - Emphasis on student-centered learning and the importance of guiding students to discover and understand content through inquiry.
 - Practical examples using the selected topics (Photosynthesis, Transport System in Plants and Animals, Nervous Coordination).

- **Method:** The session combined lectures, demonstrations, and role-play. Research assistants practiced designing a 5E lesson plan for one of the selected topics, followed by feedback.

Session 3: Training on Problem-Solving Learning Strategy

- **Objective:** Provide research assistants with the skills to implement the problem-solving strategy in the classroom.
- **Content:**
 - Introduction to problem-solving as a pedagogical approach and its benefits in enhancing critical thinking and problem-solving skills.
 - Detailed explanation of how to present real-life Biology problems to students and guide them through the problem-solving process.
 - Examples of problem-solving tasks related to the topics of Photosynthesis, Transport Systems, and Nervous Coordination.
 - Techniques for promoting collaborative problem-solving among students.
- **Method:** The session included a hands-on activity where research assistants were tasked with designing a problem-solving activity based on one of the topics. Research assistants worked in pairs to develop scenarios and solutions, which was critiqued in a group discussion.

Phase 2: Pre-testing of Students:

The pre-test helped to determine the equivalence of the groups before the experimental intervention

PHASE 3: Actual Treatment

Inquiry Based Learning Strategy:

1. Engage(stimulate Curiosity) : Begin with a thought provoking question
2. Pose a guiding Question: Present a researchable question
3. Explore: Allow students to investigate using materials, textbooks and internet
4. Explain: (students theorizing): Students share findings and propose explanation
5. Elaborate: Students apply concepts to new situations or solve related problems
6. Evaluate: Teacher gives feedback to consolidate learning.

Problem Solving Strategy

1. Define the problem: Teacher provides a curriculum based problem
2. Form Groups: divides class into small heterogenous groups
3. Brainstorm solution: Each group identifies possible solution
4. Research and analyze: students collect information and assess their ideas.
5. Choose the best solution: Group agree on a solution and justify with facts
6. Implement or simulate: Carry out their solution or simulate it through drawings or reports.
7. Present result: Each group presents findings in class
8. Evaluate: Teacher assesses based on creativity, teamwork, reasoning and accuracy.

Lecture Method (Control Group)

Step 1. Introduction: Briefly introduces the topic and objectives

Step 2. Content delivery: Teacher explains the concept

Step 3. Examples and illustration: Use real-life or textbook

Step 4. Questioning: Ask, recall and comprehension question to check understanding

Step 5. Summary: Recap main points, answer question

Step 6. Assessment

PHASE 4 : POST TESTING:

At the end of the six –week instructional period, the same Biology Achievement Test (BAT) was re-administered as a post-test to evaluate students' academic achievement.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics such as t-test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test the hypotheses. Hypotheses testing was done at 0.05 level of significance.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students taught using inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District ?*

To answer this research question, the data collected at post test were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and this is shown in Table 4.1

Table 1:

Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation showing the mean scores of Students Taught Using Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS), Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), and Lecture Method (LM)

Methods	N	Mean	SD
Inquiry learning strategy	83	61.47	9.29
Problem Solving Strategy	79	57.42	9.97
Lecture Method	89	50.23	10.70

From Table 1 it can be seen that students taught with Inquiry learning strategy obtained a mean score of 61.47 with a standard deviation of 9.29. Those taught with problem-solving strategy achieved a mean score of 57.42 with a standard deviation of 9.97 and those taught with Lecture method got a mean score of 50.23 with a standard deviation of 10.70. The table shows that those taught with Inquiry learning strategy had the highest mean score, followed by those taught with problem solving strategy, while those in the lecture method groups got the least mean score. This disparity in the mean scores of the three groups indicates a difference in the mean achievement scores of the students taught Biology using inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy and lecture method. To determine if the difference is significant, Hypothesis one was tested.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students taught using inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District

In order to determine the appropriate statistics to be used to test hypothesis one, students pre-test scores were analyzed using Analysis of variance statistics (ANOVA) to establish the equivalence of the groups and this is shown in Table 2a.

Table 2a: ANOVA statistics comparing the difference among the mean scores of students taught with Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS), Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), and Lecture Method (LM) at pre-test

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	250.505	2	125.25	1.617	0.201
Within Groups	19214.460	248	77.468		
Total	19464.964	250			

Table 2a shows that difference at pre-test is not significant, with this ANOVA statistics becomes the appropriate statistics to be used to test hypothesis one and the result is shown in Table 4.2b.

Table 2b. ANOVA statistics comparing the difference among mean scores of students taught with Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS), Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), and Lecture Method (LM) at post-test

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	5575.931	2	2787.965	27.774	0.00
Within Groups	19214.460	248	100.381		
Total	30470.382	250			

With a calculated sig value of 0.00 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05, the Table shows a significant difference among the mean scores of students taught with ILS, PSS and LM. With this hypothesis one which states that there is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students taught using inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method is rejected. In order to determine the direction of the significance, Scheffe post hoc analysis was carried out and the result is shown in Table 2c

Table 2c. Scheffe Post Hoc analysis showing the direction of significant among the mean scores of students taught with ILS, PSS and LM

(I)Methods	(J) Methods	Mean Diff (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig	95% Confidence Level	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
ILS	PSS	4.05	1.57	0.038	0.17	7.93
	LM	11.22	1.53	0.00	7.46	14.99
PSS	ILS	4.05	1.57	0.038	7.93	0.17
	LM	7.17	1.77	0.00	3.36	10.98
LM	ILS	11.22	1.53	0.00	14.99	7.46
	PSS	7.17	1.54	0.00	10.98	3.36

Table 2c shows that the direction of the difference is between ILS and PSS, ILS and LM in favour of the students taught with inquiry learning strategy.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the inquiry learning strategy in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District?

To answer the research question, the data collected at post test were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the result is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Mean and Standard Deviation statistics showing the mean scores of male and female biology students taught with inquiry learning instructional strategy.

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD
Male	43	62.44	2.01	10.12
Female	40	60.43		8.29

Table 3 shows that the male students taught with inquiry learning strategy had a mean score of 62.44 with a standard deviation of 10.12 and the female students had a mean score of 60.43 with a standard deviation of 8.29. There exists a mean difference of 2.01 in favour of the male students. To determine if the difference is significant, independent sample t-test statistics was used to test hypothesis two.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the inquiry learning strategy in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District.

In order to determine the appropriate statistics to be used to test hypothesis two, male and female students pre-test scores were analyzed using independent sample t-test statistics to establish the equivalence of the groups and this is shown in Table 4a

Table 4a

Independent sample t-test Statistics showing the mean scores of male and female students taught with inquiry learning instructional strategy at pre-test.

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD	df	tcal	Sig (2-tailed)
Male	43	23.02		9.94			
			0.81		81	0.09	0.93
Female	40	23.20		7.64			

Table 4a shows that the difference is not significant at pre-test, since the calculated Sig value of 0.93 which is greater than the sig value of alpha sig value of 0.05 was obtained. With this, students independent sample t-test statistics was used to test H_{02} and the result is shown in Table 4.4b.

Table 4b

Independent sample t-test statistics showing the mean scores of male and female students taught with inquiry learning instructional strategy.

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD	df	tcal	Sig(2-tailed)
Male	43	62.44		10.12			
			2.01		81	0.99	0.33
Female	40	60.43		8.29			

Table 4b shows that the observed difference in Table 4.4 is not significant, since the critical sig value of 0.33 which is greater than alpha value of 0.05 was obtained. With this, H_{02} which states that there is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the inquiry learning strategy is not rejected.

Research Question 3: *What is the difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the problem-solving strategy in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District?*

To answer the research question, the data collected at post test were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the result is shown in Table 4.5a

Table 5a

Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation showing the mean scores of male and female biology students taught with Problem solving strategy

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD
Male	59	57.28		10.38
			0.52	
Female	20	57.80		8.90

Table 5a shows that the male students taught with Problem solving strategy had a mean score of 57.28 with a standard deviation of 10.38 and the female students had a mean score of 57.80 with a standard deviation of 8.90. There exist a mean difference of 0.52 in favour of the female students. To determine if the difference is significant, hypothesis three was tested.

H_{03} : There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the problem-solving strategy in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District.

In order to determine the appropriate statistics to be used to test hypothesis three, male and female students pre-test scores were analyzed using independent sample t-test statistics to establish the equivalence of the groups and this is shown in Table 5b

Table 5b

Independent sample t-test statistics showing the mean scores of male and female students taught with Problem Solving strategy at pre-test.

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD	t	df	Sig
Male	59	22.22	6.22	8.50	2.71	77	0.008
Female	20	16.00		9.92			

Table 5b shows that the difference is significant at pre-test, since the calculated Sig value of 0.008 which is less than the alpha sig value of 0.05 was obtained. With this, Analysis of Co-Variance statistics was used to test H_{03} and the result is shown in Table 5c.

Table.5c Analysis of Covariance Statistics comparing the difference in mean scores of male and female students taught with PSS

Source	Type 111 Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected Model	403.680	2	201.840	2.087	0.131
Intercept	36012.220	1	36012.220	372.385	0.000
Pre-test	399.767	1	399.767	4.134	0.046
Sex	60.641	1	60.641	0.627	0.431
Error	7349.535	76	96.704		
Total	268200.000	79			
Corrected Total	7753.215	78			

Table 5c shows that the difference in the mean scores of male and female students is not significant since the calculated sig value of 0.431 which is greater than 0.05 was obtained. With this H_{03} which states that there is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using the PSS strategy is not rejected.

Research Question 4: *What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female Biology students taught using lecture method in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District ?*

To answer this research question, the data collected at post test were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and this is shown Table 6

Table 4.6

Mean and Standard Deviation statistics showing the mean scores of male and female students taught with Lecture Method.

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD
Male	47	50.30	0.11	8.74
Female	42	50.19		12.65

Table 6 shows that the male students taught with Lecture method had a mean score of 50.30 with a standard deviation of 8.74 and their female counterpart had a mean score of 50.19 with a standard

deviation of 12.65. From the mean scores, it can be seen that the male students had the highest mean score with a mean difference of 0.11. To determine if the difference is significant, H_{04} was tested.

H_{04} : There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female Biology students taught using lecture method in Secondary School in Delta Central Senatorial District.

In order to determine the appropriate statistics to be used to test hypothesis four, male and female students pre-test scores were analyzed using independent sample t-test statistics to determine the equivalence of the groups and this is shown in Table 7a

Table 7a. Independent sample t-test statistics showing the mean scores of male and female students taught with Lecture Method at pre-test.

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD	t	df	Sig
Male	47	23.06	1.82	8.30	1.029	87	0.306
Female	42	21.24		8.42			

Table 7a shows that the difference is not significant at pre-test, since the calculated Sig value of 0.306 which is greater than the alpha sig value of 0.05 was obtained. With this, independent sample t-test statistics was used to test H_{05} and the result is shown in Table 7b

Table 7b Independent sample t-test statistics showing the mean scores of male and female students taught with Lecture Method

Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD	t	df	Sig
Male	47	50.30	0.11	8.74	0.049	87	0.963
Female	42	50.19		12.65			

Table 7b shows that the difference is not significant, since the calculated Sig value of 0.963 which is greater than the alpha sig value of 0.05 was obtained. With this H_{04} which states that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of Biology students taught using lecture method is not rejected.

Research Question five: *What is the interaction effect of instructional strategies (inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method) and sex on students' mean academic achievement scores in Biology in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District ?*

To answer this research question, the data collected at post test were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and this is shown in Table 8

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation showing the interaction mean scores of Students Taught Using Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS), Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), and Lecture Method (LM)

Methods	Sex	N	Mean	MeanDiff	SD
Inquiry learning strategy		83	61.47		9.29
Problem Solving Strategy		79	57.42		9.97
Lecture Method		89	50.23		10.70
Inquiry Learning Strategy	Male	43	62.44	2.01	10.12
	Female	40	60.43		8.29
Problem Solving Strategy	Male	59	57.28	0.52	10.38
	Female	20	57.80		8.90

Lecture Method	Male	47	50.30		8.74
				0.11	
	Female	42	50.19		12.65

From Table 8, it can be seen that students taught with Inquiry learning strategy obtained an interaction mean score of 61.47 with a standard deviation of 9.29. Those taught with problem-solving strategy achieved an interaction mean score of 57.42 with a standard deviation of 9.97 and those taught with Lecture method got an interaction mean score of 50.23. The table shows that, those taught with Inquiry learning strategy had the highest interaction mean score, followed by those taught with problem solving strategy, while those in the lecture method groups got the least interaction mean score.. The Table also, shows that the male students taught with inquiry learning strategy had an interaction mean score of 62.44 with a standard deviation of 10.12 and the female students had an interaction mean score of 60.43 with a standard deviation of 8.29. There exists a difference of 2.01 in favour of the male students. In addition, the table shows that the male students taught with Problem solving strategy had an interaction mean score of 57.28 with a standard deviation of 10.38 and the female students had an interaction mean score of 57.80 with a standard deviation of 8.90. There exist an interaction mean difference of 0.52 in favour of the female students. Furthermore, the Table shows that the male students taught with Lecture method had an interaction mean score of 50.30 with a standard deviation of 8.74 and their female counterpart had an interaction mean score of 50.19 with a standard deviation of 12.65. From the interaction mean scores, it can be seen that the male students had the highest interaction mean score with a mean difference of 0.11. The differences in the interaction mean scores shows that there is an interaction effect between methods and sex on students' achievements. To determine if the difference in the interaction effect is significant, H_{05} was tested using Analysis of Co-variance statistics and the result is shown on Table 4.17

H_{05} : There is no significant interaction effect of instructional strategies (inquiry learning strategy, problem-solving strategy, and lecture method) and sex on students' mean academic achievement scores in Biology in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District.

To test the hypothesis, the data collected at both pre-test and post-test were analyzed with Analysis of Co-variance statistics and the result is shown in Table 9

Table 9. Analysis of Covariance Statistics comparing the interaction effects between methods and sex on achievement

Source	Type 111 Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected Model	9535.380	6	1589.230	18.523	0.00
Intercept	74248.714	1	74248.714	865.378	0.00
Pre-test	3870.985	1	3870.985	45.117	0.00
Methods	5493.786	2	2746.893	32.015	0.00
Sex	23.990	1	23.990	0.280	0.597
Method*Sex	257.151	2	128.575	1.499	0.226
Error	20935.003	244	85.799		
Total	823666.000	251			
Corrected Total	30470.382	250			

Table 9 shows that the difference in the mean interaction effects between method and sex on achievement is not significant since the calculated sig value of 0.226 which is greater than 0.05 was obtained. With this H_{09} which states that there is no significant interaction effect between methods and sex on achievement.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study's first finding shows that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement scores of students taught using the different instructional strategies, with the Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS) showing the highest improvement in student academic achievement. Students taught using ILS demonstrated a substantial mean gain of 61.47, indicating that ILS had a stronger impact on their academic achievement compared to the Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS) and the Lecture Method (LM), which had mean gains of 57.42 and 50.23 points, respectively. This finding suggests that ILS is more effective in enhancing student academic performance in Biology. This could be because ILS approach involves an active, student-centred learning environment where learners explore, question, and engage deeply with the content. This aligns with the constructivist theory of learning, which emphasises that students construct their own understanding through experiences rather than passively absorbing information. The active participation and critical thinking encouraged in ILS may explain the higher achievement scores. The strategy likely promotes better understanding by involving students in discovering information on their own, making the learning process more meaningful and lasting and this is reflected in their achievement. Supporting past findings this result align with that Abu (2023), Abubakar and Ogunleye (2021) and that of Adewale and Kolawole (2019) who found that students taught with guided inquiry strategies in Biology showed improved academic achievement compared to those taught with conventional methods, which aligns with the current study's findings.

The second, third and fourth findings of the study also shows that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement scores between male and female students taught using the Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS), Problem Solving strategy and lecture method. For the ILS, the male students outperformed their female counterparts. Male students achieved a mean score of 62.44, while female students scored 60.43, resulting in a mean difference of 2.01 points in favour of the male students. This finding indicates that male students taught with ILS demonstrated better academic performance compared to female students and this was found not to be significant (Table 4.4b). For the PSS group there was no a significant difference in the academic achievement scores between male and female students taught using the Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), with female students outperforming their male counterparts. Female students achieved a mean score of 57.80, while male students scored 57.28, resulting in a mean difference of 0.52 in favour of female students. This suggests that female students taught with PSS demonstrated better academic performance compared to their male peers but this was not significant as shown in Table 4.5c. Lastly, for the Lecture Method, that the male students taught with Lecture method had a mean score of 50.30 and their female counterpart had a mean score of 50.19. From the mean scores, it can be seen that the male students had the highest mean score with a mean difference of 0.11. However this was not found to be significant in Table 4.7a.

This finding disagrees with previous research of Ajai and Imoko (2015) Ajayi and Olanrewaju (2019), Alabi and Iyiola (2020), Ibe and Ozoemena (2021), Ibe and Agommuoh (2022), who found significant differences in the students achievement based on sex but agrees with Agboro-Eravwoke (2022), Agboro-Eravwoke, Edah, & Iyayi, (2025) who found a non significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught with same teaching methods.

Lastly, the fifth finding of the study also shows that there is no significant interaction effects between instructional strategies (Inquiry Learning Strategy, Problem-Solving Strategy, and Lecture Method) and sex on students' mean academic achievement scores in Biology. This interaction effect was particularly noticeable for students taught using the Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS), where male students with higher pretest scores performed worse in the posttest compared to their female counterparts. The non significant interaction effect suggests that the effectiveness of instructional strategies does not depend on the sex of the students. This shows that both male and female students benefitted almost at the same levels when the strategy was used hence the non significant difference found. This findings agrees with the findings of Agboro-Eravwoke, Iyayi and Edah (2025), who found no significant effects between methods and sex on students achievement but disagrees with that of Ibe and Agommuoh (2022), Ajai and Imoko (2015), Akpan and Akanwa (2024), who found a significant interaction effect between instructional strategies and sex on academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that instructional strategies play a critical role in enhancing the academic achievement and retention of Biology students. The findings revealed that the Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS) and Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS) were significantly more effective than the Lecture Method (LM) in improving students' academic achievement and long-term retention of biological concepts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should incorporate Inquiry Learning Strategy (ILS) and Problem-Solving Strategy (PSS) into their instructional practices to enhance student engagement, academic achievement, and retention in Biology and other science subjects.
2. Teachers should be mindful of sex differences in student achievement, as male and female students may respond differently to various teaching strategies. While male students performed better with ILS and female students excelled in PSS, it is important for educators to tailor their teaching methods to the specific learning needs and strengths of both sexes.
3. There is a need for ongoing professional development programmes for Biology teachers, focusing on the implementation of inquiry-based and problem-solving instructional strategies. Teachers should be trained in using these methods effectively to maximise their impact on student learning outcomes.

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